

Supplementary Table S1: Goodness of fit comparisons for generalised linear mixed models of catches of various PCR-identified *Anopheles* mosquitoes, using either Poisson or two forms of negative binomial distribution, each with and without zero inflation, expressed in terms of the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) estimates for each of these different models with different distributions for the dependent variables. Lower AIC values indicate a better model fit, so the lowest AIC estimate for each species are highlighted in bold, indicating the best fit models detailed in table 2. For all these models, IRS regime was included as a categorical fixed effect with DDT+CD micro-mosaic treated as the reference group. Also, in all these models, HFCA was treated as a random effect, within which first order temporal auto correlation was nested, treating the number of months since the start of the study as the incremental time step unit.

<i>Anopheles</i> taxon	Poisson		Negative Binomial		Negative Binomial	
			Type 1		Type 2	
	No Zero Inflation	With Zero Inflation	No Zero Inflation	With Zero Inflation	No Zero Inflation	With Zero Inflation
<i>Anopheles gambiae</i> complex						
<i>An. arabiensis</i>	3429	2737	2273.6	2262	2274	2276
<i>An. quadriannulatus</i>	1089	1000	926.3	NE	904	896
<i>An. funestus</i> group						
<i>An. funestus</i>	694	668	605	607	609	610
<i>An. parensis</i>	2648	2182	1871	1845	1814	1813
<i>An. rivulorum</i>	1079	1047	933	NE	928	927

NE: Not Estimable because the model in question failed to fit.